

OPTIMIZATION OF ADJUSTABLE SPEED-PERMANENT MAGNET SYNCHRONOUS MOTOR (AS-PMSM) BY USING PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION(PSO)

¹Prof. Lokesh T. R, ²Dr.Umadevi. D, ³Mr. Vinod kumar H, ⁴Mr.Vishnu Prasad D

^{1,2}Assistant Professor, Department of EEE, Dr. Ambedkar Institute of Technology Bengaluru

^{3,4}Bachelor of Engineering, Department of EEE, Dr. Ambedkar institute of technology Bengaluru

Abstract—This study investigates the design and optimization of adjustable speed permanent magnet synchronous motor (AS-PMSM) for EV's applications. The AS-PMSM is recognized for its high torque density, high efficiency making it suitable for EV's. this study designed for high performance 110kw AS-PMSM for EV's applications. This study uses theoretical calculations, PSO algorithm and FEM based ANSYS MAXWELL software for optimization and validation of motor design of AS-PMSM.

Keywords—AS-PMSM, DESIGN, PSO, EFFICIENCY, ANSYS MAXWELL.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric vehicles (EVs) are becoming increasingly popular due to their environmental benefits and cost-effectiveness. The performance and efficiency of EVs are heavily dependent on their electric motors. Permanent magnet synchronous motors (PMSMs) are widely used in EVs due to their high torque density, high efficiency, and low production costs. However, the design of PMSMs is complex and requires careful optimization to achieve the desired performance. PMSMs are designed to operate in a wide range of speeds and loads. The design parameters of PMSMs, such as the number of poles, the rotor structure, and the stator design, significantly impact their performance. The PSO algorithm is a popular optimization technique used to optimize the design parameters of PMSMs. ANSYS-Maxwell is a software tool used to simulate and analyze the performance of PMSMs.

Due to the reasons such as decreasing of oil resources, increasing oil prices and increase in environmental pollution it is necessary to look up towards electric-driven vehicles has been increasing now a days. Use of comprehensive approach to ensure that the motors design meets the required performance criteria for EV's under various operating conditions [1]. Development of Electric vehicle technology to environmentalist approaches [2-3]. Optimization of engine shape using parameter optimization method to check the durability of engine mounts [4] and ferro graphic oil analysis for monitoring the diesel engine wear [5-6]. colony optimization algorithm is applied to optimize the sequencing of cars on production lines, improving efficiency and reducing production costs [7]. Today, most automotive manufacturers concentrate on research and development activities in the field of electric vehicles which leads to better performance and fuel efficiency [8]. Many optimization problems arise when designing automobile engines. So that the researchers focus on the development and calibration of an electronic control system for CNG engines because of the emission characteristics of CNG engines [9-10]. Many involve multiple conflicting purposes. One of the most important stages in

engine design is engine calibration, which is the adjusts the internal combustion engine or control unit so that engine power achieves optimal fuel performance [11]. Using artificial neural networks to diesel engine modeling [12], using polynomial neural networks for modeling and multi-objective optimization of a variable valve-timing spark-ignition engine [13] and using an evolving local model network for combustion engine modeling [14]. Modeling is done for different reasons. An example of this is the design and optimization of the controller system. Designing a controller using the real motor during the design process is an expensive and time-consuming action. For this reason, many researchers first build a model of the engine and then design, test and optimize their controllers on that model.

The efficiency of the electric motor, which is the key component of the electric drive system, is crucial because efficient energy use is required [15–17]. design and analyze a magnetic-gear permanent magnet synchronous motor for driving electric vehicles. The study emphasizes the advantages of magnetic gearing in enhancing the performance and efficiency of electric vehicle motors [18]. Utilizing drive systems that consume the least amount of energy per unit of distance per kilometer [19]. Design and optimization of surface permanent magnet synchronous motors using a design assist system which provides practical insights into the challenges and solutions in the industrial implementation of these motors for industrial applications [20-22]. analysis of magnetic materials with the developments in magnetic materials and motor topologies, advances in electric motor designs [23]. Electric vehicles consist of four main subsystems are battery control system, electric propulsion system, electric motor driver and vehicle main control unit. battery system supplies the required power for the vehicles. The battery control system constantly monitors the the temperature and charge status of the battery, depending on the power needs of varying duration and value, and transmits information to the vehicle main control unit. An electric motor is used in the vehicle propulsion system.

AS-PMSM can be used in electric vehicles. In this study, the design and analysis of 110kw AS-PMSM at maximum operation for an electric vehicle propulsion system is demonstrated. The required results are achieved by running the design equations and specific parameters of PMSM into MATLAB Simulation, which is performed by the PSO [24-26]. And then the magnetic analysis of PMSM is realized by using FEM-based ANSYS MAXWELL 2D software (ANSYS Electronics Desktop). As a result, designed electric motor provides the high efficiency with less losses depending on the design constraints [27].

II. DESIGN

A. Permanent magnet synchronous motor

In recent years, Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSM) are widely used in industrial applications like especially electric vehicles because of the valuable features such as high efficiency, high power factor and ratio of torque to weight, and fast response. The surface mounted PMSM with sinusoidal EMF is used in this study. PMSM has three stator windings and the rotor of the motor has surface mounted permanent magnets.

B. Block Diagram

Fig. 1: work flow diagram

As the block diagram suggest the work flow this project is of this order by the reference paper mentioned earlier the 110kW Adjustable speed PMSM is taken with specified parameters and using this design is done in the ANSYS software and to optimize the parameter PSO algorithm is implemented with the help of MATLAB programming and hence again need to create the ANSYS simulation and compare both the simulated output.

C. Mathematical model

Copper losses calculations

$$P_{Cu} = 3 * i^2 * R$$

Where i is the current and R is the resistance.

Iron losses calculations

$$P_{iron} = K_e * B_{max}^\alpha * f^\beta * V_{core}$$

Where K_e , α and β are material coefficients, B_{max} is maximum flux density, f is frequency, V_{core} is core volume.

Efficiency calculations

$$efficiency = \frac{P_{in} - P_{loss}}{P_{in}}$$

$$\text{Where } P_{loss} = P_{Cu} + P_{iron}$$

Wire diameter calculations

$$dwire = \sqrt{\frac{i}{\pi * j}}$$

Where i is phase current and j is current density.

D. Design parameters

The normal voltage selected for 110 KW motors is 220 V because which is the lowest value of the battery. So that the motor is designed to provide required torque at the low battery voltage. The motor electrical design should be balanced between the nominal and maximum power value for its better performance i.e the current density value selected should closely related to the max value for normal operation of the motor which results in max power will drawn by motor for long duration as long as possible.

Table 1: Basic parameters of motor

Name	Value
Operation Type	Motor
Load Type	Constant Power
Rated Output Power	85.9 kW
Maximum power	110kW
Rated Voltage	220 V
Maximum Speed	13300 rpm
Operating Temperature	75 ⁰ C

The drive motor is one of the subsystems of the electric vehicle such as battery, driver, control unit and battery control system. For this reason, there are also constraints related to other subsystems in engine design. Data affecting engine design depending on other subsystems are given in Table 1, Before starting the motor design, in addition to the performance values specified in Table 1, electrical and magnetic parameters should also be determined. These values used in the design are given in Table 2. [27]

The dimensions of the motor were determined by using the values specified in Table 1 and Table 2. While determining the dimensions of the motor, the output coefficient method was used [18,19]. Depends upon on the predetermined design values, the dimensioning of the motor such as stator, rotor, slot, winding, pole design has been done. The thickness of the lamination material used is 0.3 mm, the magnetic saturation value is 2.4 T and the iron loss is 1.046 kW. Depending on the analytical and magnetic analysis results, improvements were made in the design. ANSYS RMxprt is used for motor design and Maxwell-2D software is used for magnetic field analysis.

Table 2: Electrical and magnetic parameters

Name	Value
Stator-Teath Flux Density	0.78 T
Stator-Yoke Flux Density	0.79 T
Rotor-Yoke Flux Density	0.43 T
Air-Gap Flux Density	0.63 T
Magnet Flux Density	0.98 T
Stator Teeth Ampere Turn	2.4 AT
Stator Yoke Ampere Turn	2.7 AT
Rotor Yoke Ampere Turn	0.96 AT

Fig 2. Stator and rotor construction.

Table 3: Stator & Rotor parameters

Name	Value
Outer diameter of the stator core	300mm
Inner diameter of the stator core	217mm
Length of the stator core	75mm
Stacking Factor	0.95
Steel type of the stator core	M27_29G
Outer diameter of the rotor core	210mm
Inner diameter of the rotor core	145mm
Length of the rotor core	75mm
Steel type of the rotor core	M27_29G

III. ANALYSIS OF PMSM WITH PARICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION

PSO was developed in 1995 by J. Kennedy and R. C. Eberhart [24]. PSO is a heuristic algorithm based on swarm intelligence and it is a population-based stochastic algorithm, i.e. it works

on a set of solutions and is random in nature. It is inspired by the behavior of birds flocking and fishes schooling. Let us Consider the several birds flying in a group, each bird in the group will be considered as a particle and the entire group will be considered as a swarm. this algorithm takes a set of candidate solutions as an input. Here, every solution in the group is known as a particle and the entire set of solutions is known as swarm and the goal is to achieve an optimal solution, hence it is known as PSO algorithm.

Fig 3. shows the flowchart of the PSO algorithm. This algorithm, similar to the genetic algorithm, starts with an initial set of candidate solutions. The fitness function calculates the fitness value of each candidate solution. The goal is to maximize (or minimize) this fitness value. The term “pbest” indicates the personal best fitness value of a given particle in its history, while the term “gbest” indicates the global best fitness value of all particles for that iteration. and then based on the pbest and gbest values, the velocity for each particle is calculated and the position of the particle is changed based on its velocity.

$$V_i^{k+1} = v_i^k + c_1 * rand_1^k * (pbest_i^k - X_i^k) + c_2 * rand_2^k * (gbest_i^k - X_i^k) \text{-----}(1)$$

$$X_i^{k+1} = X_i^k + V_i^{k+1} \text{-----}(2)$$

Eq. (1) is used to update the velocity of the particle and Eq. (2) is use to update the position of the particle, where V_i is the velocity of the particle, X_i is position of the particle, “rand” is random number generator, K is the number of iterations and variables $C1$ and $C2$ are the accelerating coefficients which can be adjusted by the user to modify the rate of change in position.

Fig 3. Flowchart of PSO

Table 4: PSO parameters

Parameter	Value
Population size	100
Maximum iteration	100
Cognitive constant	2
Social constant	2
Max inertia weight	0.9
Min inertia weight	0.4

The optimum parameter values for the particle swarm optimization algorithm in the developed Matlab program are given in Table 4. The optimum engine values were obtained by running the PSO code in MATLAB.

A. PSO initialization:

PSO Iterations

Update inertia weight

$$w = w_{max} - \left(\frac{w_{max} - w_{min}}{\max_iter} \right) * iter$$

Objective Function Evaluation:

Calculate P_{cu} , P_{iron} , efficiency, and wire diameter for each particle.

The fitness function is:

Update Velocities and Positions:

$$V_i^{k+1} = v_i^k + c_1 * rand_1^k * (pbest_i^k - X_i^k) + c_2 * rand_2^k * (gbest_i^k - X_i^k)$$

$$X_i^{k+1} = X_i^k + V_i^{k+1}$$

B. Developed MATLAB code output by using PSO:

Iteration 100: Best fitness = -0.952605

Optimal values found:

Copper Loss: 331.7 W

Iron Loss: 1046.4264 W

Efficiency: 95.2605 %

Wire Diameter: 0.0024722m

C. Manual calculations:

Given parameters:

Current, $I = 96$ A

Resistance, $R = 0.012 \Omega$

Maximum flux density, $B_{max} = 1.41$ T

Frequency, $f = 50$ Hz

Core volume, $V_{core} = 0.005$ m³

Material coefficients, $ke = 1.0$, $\alpha = 1.5$, $\beta = 3.0$

Input power, $P_{input} = 110$ kW

Copper losses calculations.

$$P_{Cu} = 3 * 96^2 * 0.012 = 331.7$$

Iron losses calculations.

$$P_{iron} = 1.0 * 1.41^{1.5} * 50^3 * 0.005 = 1046.4$$

Efficiency calculations.

$$P_{loss} = 331.7 + 1046.4 = 1378.1$$

$$efficiency = \frac{110000 - 1378.9}{110000} = 0.9525 * 100 = 95.25\%$$

Wire diameter calculations, assume $j = 5 * 10^6$ A/m²

$$dwire = \sqrt{\frac{96}{\pi * 5 * 10^6}} = 0.0024 \text{ m}$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

• EFFICIENCY CURVE

Fig 4. Efficiency curve

Fig 4. is the efficiency curve shows that the motor achieves a high efficiency of 96.8% at the rated torque. This indicates that the motor design, including factors like stator and rotor geometry, winding configuration, and magnet design, has been optimized to minimize losses and maximize efficiency.

• Cogging torque curve

Fig.5.Cogging Torque Curvef

Fig 5. represents the swing torque of the electric motor when it is running at no load. The curve shows that the torque is small and has a peak-to-peak value of 0.35 Nm. This information is part of the analysis results obtained from the Finite Element Model of the motor created using ANSYS which was used to simulate the electromagnetic field and obtain the structural parameters of the motor.

- **Airgap flux density**

Fig 6. Airgap flux density curve

Fig 6. is the air gap flux density plot allows evaluating if the motor design, including factors like stator slot geometry, rotor pole shape, and magnet design, which results in the desired flux density distribution.

- **Torque curve**

Fig 7. Torque curve at operating condition

Fig 7. shows that evaluating the torque quality of the PMSM under rated load conditions by visualizing the torque ripple. In this figure the low vibration level indicates the motor design is optimized to provide the required rated torque with minimum torque ripple.

- **Winding current curve**

Fig 8. Winding current curve at rated operating condition

Fig 8. Shows that distribution of winding currents at the rated operating condition of the Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor designed for electric vehicle applications. The figure displays the analytically calculated currents applied to the motor windings in the nominal operating condition. This information is crucial for understanding how the currents flow

through the motor windings, which directly impacts the motor's electromagnetic performance, torque production and efficiency.

View of flux density distribution in ANSYS MAXWELL 2D:

Fig 9. represents the flux density distribution within the motor core when operating at its rated conditions. This figure is critical for assessing the motor's performance and identifying potential issues like, magnetic saturation.

It includes: General Flux Density: The flux density values do not exceed 2 Tesla (T), which indicates that the motor is operating within its optimal magnetic limits.

Narrow Areas and Overhangs: There are some occasional overhangs in narrow areas such as the openings of the gutters, but these values remain below the magnetic saturation limit of 2.4T for the material used.

Material Utilization: The figure demonstrates effective utilization of the motor's magnetic material, ensuring that the design avoids magnetic saturation while maintaining efficient operation.

Fig 9: Flux Density Distribution at Rated Operating Condition

View of flux lines distribution in ANSYS MAXWELL 2D

Fig 10: Flux line Distribution at Rated Operating Condition

Fig 10. illustrates the distribution of magnetic flux lines within the motor during its nominal operating condition. These lines show how the flux flows from magnets to stator through airgap. The color map represents the variation of magnetic flux density within the motor which helps to understand the electromagnetic performance of the motor.

Table 5. Analysis Results of PMSM

parameters	Optimization of PMSM Without PSO	Optimization of PMSM With PSO
Maximum line induced voltage	249.7 V	249.7 V
Input DC current	302.86 mA	375.5 mA
Input power	90.6 KW	109 KW
Output power	84.8 KW	112 KW
Rated torque	60.9 N-M	78.3 N-M
Flux density	1.40T	1.41 T
Synchronous speed	13300 rpm	13300 rpm
Operating temperature	75 ^o C	75 ^o C
Wire diameter	0.962 mm	2.5 mm
Iron loss	1043 W	1043 W
Copper loss	358.6 W	307.9 W
Efficiency	93.4 %	96.8 %

As shown in the table 5, by using values specified in the table 1,2 and 3 PMSM is designed in ANSYS RMxprt software and the values obtained for the Optimization of PMSM Without PSO is as shown above [27]. Similarly in this study the geometrical structure of the PMSM is not changed but it is optimized with help of PSO algorithm (table 4) to obtain the optimized values such as wire diameter, copper loss, iron loss and efficiency and then magnetic analysis of PMSM carried out for its optimized values. As a result of this Optimization of PMSM With PSO has reduced copper loss, increased efficiency and better performance than Optimization of PMSM Without PSO is as shown in the table 5.

V. CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates the design and analysis of a 110 KW AS-PMSM motor for electric vehicle applications using the PSO algorithm and ANSYS-Maxwell software. The design parameters and winding parameters of the PMSM are optimized to reduce copper losses of the motor. The winding of the PMSM is rewound by 2.5mm diameter copper wire. Then, Maxwell 2D analysis of the PMSM is realized according to the new winding. Magnetic flux density and flux lines are obtained by Maxwell 2D analysis. It is observed that the copper losses of the PMSM reduce from 358.6 W to 307.9 W. Besides, the heating problem of the motor is also solved by this optimization method. As a result, it is seen that copper loss is reduced and efficiency is

improved by increasing the wire diameter in Optimized PMSM design with PSO than that of the non-optimized PMSM design.

REFERENCES

1. *Propulsion Motor for Electric Conversion Vehicle Based on Vehicle Driving Performance Simulation.* IEEE Transportation Electrification Conference and Expo, Busan, South Korea, pp. 412–416.
2. Bouscayrol, Alain, et al. "Special Section on Advanced Powertrains for More Electric Vehicles." *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 6, no. 3, 2016, pp. 995–997.
3. Zhu, S., et al. "Iron Loss and Efficiency Analysis of Interior PM Machines for Electric Vehicle Applications." *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 65, no. 1, 2018, pp. 114–124.
4. Özüpak, Yildirim. "Efficiency Analysis of BLDC for Variable Magnetic Field." *MANAS Journal of Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 1, 2022.
5. Belmondo, A., et al. "Optimization of Ferrographic Oil Analysis for Diesel Engine Wear Monitoring." *Wear*, vol. 90, no. 1, 1983, pp. 49–61.
6. Kim, J. J., and H. Y. Kim. "Shape Design of an Engine Mount by a Method of Parameter Optimization." *Computers & Structures*, vol. 65, no. 5, 1997, pp. 725–731.
7. Gagne, C., et al. "Solving Real Car Sequencing Problems with Ant Colony Optimization." *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 174, no. 3, 2006, pp. 1427–1448.
8. Lowe, D., and K. Zapart. "Validation of Neural Networks in Automotive Engine Calibration." *International Conference on Artificial Neural Networks*, 1997, pp. 221–226.
9. Zeng, K., et al. "Development and Calibration on an Electronic Control System of CNG Engine." *IEEE International Conference on Vehicular Electronics and Safety*, 2006, pp. 204–208.
10. Vong, C., et al. "Case-Based Reasoning for Automotive Engine Electronic Control Unit Calibration." *International Conference on Information and Automation*, 2009, pp. 1380–1385.
11. Rosato, A., and S. Sibilio. "Calibration and Validation of a Model for Simulating Thermal and Electric Performance of an Internal Combustion Engine-Based Micro-Cogeneration Device." *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vols. 45–46, 2012, pp. 79–98.
12. Brzozowska, L., et al. "An Application of Artificial Neural Network to Diesel Engine Modelling." *Intelligent Data Acquisition and Advanced Computing Systems, IEEE*, 2005, pp. 142–146.
13. Atashkari, K., et al. "Modelling and Multi-Objective Optimization of a Variable Valve-Timing Spark-Ignition Engine Using Polynomial Neural Networks and Evolutionary Algorithms." *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 48, no. 3, 2007, pp. 1029–1041.
14. Hametner, C., and S. Jakubek. "Combustion Engine Modelling Using an Evolving Local Model Network." *IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems*, 2011, pp. 2802–2807.
15. Liu, J., et al. "Influence Research of Rotor Structure Parameters on the Performance of IPMSM." *20th International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems (ICEMS)*, 2017, pp. 1–5.

16. Rakesh, K., and P. Sanjeevikumar. "Electric Vehicles for India: Overview and Challenges." *IEEE India Info*, vol. 14, no. 2, 2019.
17. Bozhidar, S., et al. "Finite Element Analysis of Rotating Electrical Machines—An Educational Approach." *IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON)*, 2017.
18. Chan, B. P., and Geochul J. "Design and Analysis of Magnetic-Geared Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor for Driving Electric Vehicles." *IEEE International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems (ICEMS)*, 2017.
19. Emma, A. G., and Torbjörn T. "Performance Analysis of Current BEVs Based on a Comprehensive Review of Specifications." *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification*, vol. 2, no. 3, 2016.
20. Yamano, K., et al. "Basic Study on Design of Surface Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor Using Design Assist System of PMSM." *IEEE International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems (ICEMS)*, 2016.
21. Yamazaki, K., et al. "IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications." vol. 49, 2013, pp. 2478–2486.
22. Özüpak, Yıldırım. "Investigation of the Effect of Design Parameters of Small Brushless DC Motors on Motor Performance by Finite Element Method." *Brilliant Engineering*, vol. 3, 2022, pp. 46–58.
23. Claudio, B., et al. "IEEE Transactions on Magnetics." vol. 48, 2012, pp. 2685–2693.
24. Marini, Federico, and Beata Walczak. "Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO): A Tutorial." *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems*, vol. 149, 2015, pp. 153–165.
25. Reyes-Sierra, M., and C. A. Coello Coello. "Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimizers: A Survey of the State-of-the-Art." *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Research*, vol. 2, no. 3, 2006, pp. 287–308.
26. Shami, T. M., et al. "Particle Swarm Optimization: A Comprehensive Survey." *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, 2022, pp. 10031–10061.
27. Özüpak, Yıldırım, and Mehmet Çınar. "Optimization of PMSM by Using PSO and ANSYS Maxwell." *Adıyaman Üniversitesi Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi*, vol. 20, 2023, pp. 141–155.